
Milestone M-A2.COHERSIVE.4.10
Workpackage JIP2-WP4 Data
platform to facilitate risk-
analysis and outbreak control

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners: IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH,
IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, ISS

This milestone is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Milestone	Analysis of epi-data into tracing framework enclosed
WP and Task	JIP-WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control; T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework ST3: Integration of surveillance and outbreak data into the software platform for analysis
Leader	BfR
Other contributors	IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, ISS
Due month of the deliverable	M40
Actual submission month	M47
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	DEC, R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

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INTEGRATION OF SURVEILLANCE AND OUTBREAK DATA INTO THE SOFTWARE PLATFORM FOR ANALYSIS

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The Milestone was achieved by submitting the Deliverable D-JIP2-4.2.3 to the EJP platform end of November 2021 and providing the FCL Web tracing software platform (<https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin/>).